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Social Media and Women Economic Empowerment in Sokoto State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the influence of social media platform on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.. two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses were developed for the study. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study comprises 621,541 women in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.. Research Advisors Table (2006) was used to select a sample size of 384 women for the study. The instruments used for data collection was a 10-item instrument tagged Social Media and Women Empowerment Questionnaire (SOMAWEPQ). The instrument was subjected to the scrutiny of experts in research as well as Measurement and Evaluation. Scores emanating from the scrutiny of the experts based on its appropriateness and comprehensiveness was used to obtain a validity index of 0.78. Furthermore, it was subjected to pilot study in order to ascertain its reliability. The instruments were pilot tested on 30 students. These respondents were part of the population but not part of the sample for this study. The data obtained from the pilot test was used to compute the internal consistency of the instruments using Cronbach's Alpha reliability method. Results obtained from the exercise were used to obtain a reliability index of 0.75 respectively for the questionnaire and achievement test. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions developed for the study while independent t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings on the study showed: there is a significant influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria and there is a significant influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..The study recommended that Periodic training and capacity building programmes should be organized by non-governmental organizations for women on how they can effectively utilize social media for economic empowerment and Women should be sensitized through mentorship and leadership programmes on how they can utilize social media platforms to effectively enhance their leadership skills in political affairs.

Keywords: Social Media Platform, Women Empowerment, Economic Empowerment, Political Empowerment

INTRODUCTION

Women's political and economic representation remains low and continues to be of global interest. According to Bruno et al (2023), in January 2023 out of 195 countries in the world, there are 31 countries with a female head of government. At the head of ministerial departments, only 22.8% of women are ministers. Only 13 countries in the world have parity between men and women as ministers, i.e. 50%. In national parliaments, only 26.5% of all national parliamentarians are women (26% in sub-Saharan Africa); while in local government, women represent almost 34% of elected members of local deliberative bodies (25% in sub-Saharan Africa). Boasting over 33 million active social media users, a number projected to increase to 103 million users by 2026, Nigerians are ranked as the most addicted social media users in Africa (Statista, 2022). Social media have become a global space for expression for a broad online audience irrespective of culture, class, or geographical location. In Nigeria, the use of social media has become an inevitable mechanism of empowerment for women through accessing new knowledge and opportunities and contributing to society's economic and social development (Aina & Olayode, 2012). Social media also have become an online platform for women's activism where local issues become a global concern through hashtags and campaigns. As such, women activists have taken advantage of social media's social and economic empowerment potential. Financial empowerment is the new feminism, and women's economic empowerment will not be complete if they are not financially empowered (Blair, 2022). Hence, economic empowerment and political empowerment for women are critical to their holistic development. Nigerian women have been exposed to information and ideas that have not only changed their self-image but also led to a resistance to gender inequality and bias through different empowerment campaigns and activism for change. Thus, empowering women through social media has become a frequently cited goal of development interventions for Nigerian women (Aimua, 2021). As observed earlier, women are under-represented in terms of economic and political empowerment.

Women's economic empowerment (WEE) basically means enabling women to earn a decent living. It has taken on a variety of definitions and some times, even at the highest levels (Louise, 2025), Women's economic empowerment is the transformative, collective process through which economic systems become just, equitable, and prosperous. This process envisions a world where all women enjoy their economic and social rights, exercise their agency and power to challenge inequalities, and level the playing field. For this to happen, all women need equal rights and access to, ownership of and control over resources, assets, income, time, and their own lives.

Political empowerment of women is a crucial topic that shapes our world. It focuses on providing women with equal opportunities to participate in decision-making processes at all levels of governance. But why is this so important, and what does it really mean for society? Let's dive in and explore the concept in a simple, engaging way that you can relate to. Political empowerment of women is about creating an environment where women can actively participate in politics without barriers (Procini, 2025). It's not just about having a seat at the table; it's about having a voice that is heard and valued. When women are politically empowered, entire communities benefit. Diverse Perspectives Lead to Better Decisions. Women bring unique experiences and perspectives to the table. This diversity helps create policies that address a wider range of issues, from healthcare to education and beyond.

The relevance of women in the modern day political and economic environment cannot be over-emphasized as they are nation builders and without them, nations cannot exist. However, there is a yearning or need for them to be effectively empowered in order to fully contribute their quota to the economic and political systems of their country through involvement in the use of social media platforms that may help realize this feat, the current study is therefore geared towards examining the influence of social media platform on women economic empowerment in Sokotometropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the radical transformation that has occurred in digital technology leading to widespread use of social media, its influence has not been felt in terms of empowering women. in Sokoto metropolis.

Women in Sokoto metropolis have not been effectively empowered economically and politically and thus have limited access to economic and political opportunities. However, social media as a form digital technology has the potential to bridge these gaps by providing women with vital information that may help improve their economic and political life, it is based on this premise that the current study is geared towards examining the influence of social media platforms on women empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the influence of social media platform on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.. Specifically, the study is geared towards achieving the following objectives:

1. To determine the influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment motivation in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..
2. To determine the influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment motivation in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria?
2. How does social media platforms influence women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided this study and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..
2. There is no significant influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Review of Literature

Oluwaseun, D&Morayo, Ayoola (2020) examined the effect of illiteracy on the the use of social media by women to improve their economic status in Ogun state .The descriptive research design was adopted for the study, and a structured questionnaire was used to elicit relevant information from the respondents..A sample of 100 participants was selected for the study. Structured questionnaire was developed for the study and administered to respondents. Data collected were subjected to statistical analysis (descriptive statistics and correlational analysis) using the SPSS and Microsoft Excel application packages. The results indicated that social media platforms could be used to raise the public's awareness of goods and services, boosting businesses, and could improve women's economic status. Facebook was used more frequently than four other platforms investigated. The order of decreasing use (frequency) of the social media platforms by the women was Facebook (41%), WhatsApp (27%), YouTube (13%), Instagram (12%), and LinkedIn (7%). The disparity in the use pattern of social media platforms might be connected with the characteristic features, capabilities, ease of use, complexities of the application commands, and user's knowledge of the application. It is therefore recommended that promotion of the use of other social media platforms other than Facebook may require educating the women on the benefits of using the applications for economic empowerment.

Bruno et al (2023) examined the role of social media in improving women's political empowerment in Africa. The objective of the study was to assess the effects of social media on women's political empowerment in Africa. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study.. Based on a sample of 45 African countries, a specified and estimated panel data model using the Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (POLS) method and the System Generalized Method of Moment (S-GMM) over the period 2009–2019 was developed. A Structured questionnaire was developed and administered to respondents. . the instrument was examined and scrutinized to ascertain its clarity, appropriateness and

comprehensiveness and in the process was adjudged to be valid. Data collected based on the instrument used for data collection was analyzed using regression analysis. The findings showed that social media, as measured by the Facebook penetration rate, significantly increases women political empowerment. the study concluded social media have a high potential to redistribute the balance of power in favour of previously disadvantaged political actors, including women and minority groups. A study recommended that In order to strengthen WPE, public policies must increase women's access to social media.

METHOD

Descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The population of the study comprises 621,541 women in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State; Nigeria. Research Advisors Table (2006) was used to select a sample size of 384 women for the study. The instruments used for data collection was a 10 item instrument tagged Social Media and Women Empowerment Questionnaire (SOMAWEPQ). The instruments were subjected to the scrutiny of experts in research as well as Measurement and Evaluation. Scores emanating from the scrutiny of the experts based on its appropriateness and comprehensiveness was used to obtain a validity index of 0.78. Furthermore, it was subjected to pilot study in order to ascertain its reliability. The instruments were pilot tested on 30 students. These respondents were part of the population but not part of the sample for this study. The data obtained from the pilot test was used to compute the internal consistency of the instruments using Cronbach’s Alpha reliability method. Results obtained from the exercise were used to obtain a reliability index of 0.75 respectively for the questionnaire and achievement test. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions developed for the study while independent t-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Questions 1: *What is the influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Showing influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.

	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
1. Social media has improved my access to economic opportunities .	215	85	40	44	3.22	0.84	Agreed
2. I have been able to gain access to loans and grants through social media platforms.	175	45	80	84	2.81	0.74	Agreed
3. I have acquired new business ideas through social media..	155	100	45	84	2.58	0.71	Agreed
4. The use of social media has improved my business skills thereby improving my financial life	180	70	50	84	2.90	0.75	Agreed
5. I use social media to market my products for easy access to customers..	235	65	40	44	3.28	0.86	Agreed
Average mean					2.96	0.78	

Table 1 shows the influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.. Results indicate that the average mean value is given as 2.96. This value is above the benchmark scale mean value of 2.50 for a four point scaled questionnaire. Hence, social media platforms has a high influence on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Research Questions 2: *What is the impact of influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment motivation in Sokoto state?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Showing influence of social media platforms on women Political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis

	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
6. The use of social media has increased my political awareness.	200	55	78	51	3.05	0.79	Agreed
7. My involvement in political discussions has been enhanced through social media .	180	50	58	96	2.82	0.75	Agreed
8. I have been able to use social media to mobilize support for my preferred candidate during electoral campaigns .	155	100	45	84	2.85	0.74	Agreed
9. I easily connect with variouswomen in my political group on social media	150	80	50	124	2.77	0.73	Agreed
10. Social media has enabled me to access information about political candidates	235	65	40	44	3.28	0.86	Agreed
Average mean					2.95	0.77	

Table 2 shows the influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.. Results indicate that the average mean value is given as 2.95. This value is above the benchmark scale mean value of 2.50 for a four point scaled questionnaire. Hence, social media platforms have a high influence on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..

Table 3: t-test Statistic showing influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	Std Mean	t-cal	Sig	Remarks	Decision
Social Media Platforms	384	2.96	0.78	18.22	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Women Economic Empowerment	384	2.94	0.76				

Table 3 above shows the t-test statistics on the influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..The results showed that a t-calculated value of 18.22, the p-value of 0.000 was found to be less than 0.05. Hence, the result reveals that there is a significant influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis.

Table 5: t-test Statistic showing influence of Social Media Platforms on Women Political Empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..

Variables	N	Mean	Std Mean	t-cal	Sig	Remarks	Decision
Social Media Platforms	384	2.95	0.77	15.02	0.012	Reject H ₀	Significant
Women Political Empowerment	384	2.97	0.79				

Table 4 above shows the t-test statistics on the influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..The results showed that a t-calculated value of 15.02, the p-value of 0.012 was found to be less than 0.05. Hence, the result reveals that there is a significant influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..

DISCUSSION

Findings from the study on hypothesis one reveal there is a significant influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..This findings is in agreement with the findings from the study of Oluwaseun, Morayo and Ayoola (2020) which showed significant effect of illiteracy on the use of social media by women to improve their economic status in Ogun state .

Findings from the study on hypothesis two reveal there is a significant influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with the findings from the study of Bruno et al (2023) which showed that social media played a significant role in improving women's political empowerment in Africa

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were made:

1. There is a significant influence of social media platforms on women economic empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..
2. There is a significant influence of social media platforms on women political empowerment in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria..

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study and conclusion, the following recommended were made:

1. Periodic training and capacity building programmes should be organized by non-governmental organizations for women on how they can effectively utilize social media for economic empowerment.
2. Women should be sensitized through mentorship and leadership programmes on how they can utilize social media platforms to effectively enhance their leadership skills in political affairs.

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